

Characterization of *Pantoea agglomerans* Strains Isolated from Olive Knot disease in Morocco

Bouaichi .A^{1*}, R. Benkirane², A.AMEUR³, S.SADIK⁴, A. Benbouazza⁵, and E. H Achbani⁶

^{1,5,6} *Laboratory of Phytobacteriology and Biocontrol, National Institute of Agronomic Research Meknes, Morocco.*

² *Laboratory of Botany, Biotechnology and Plant Protection, Kenitra, Morocco.*

³ *Laboratory of Virology, Microbiology and Quality / Ecotoxicology and Biodiversity, University Hassan II Mohammedia FSTM. Morocco.*

⁴ *Laboratory of Plant Biotechnology and Molecular Biology, Faculty of Sciences, Meknes, Morocco*

Email: *bouaichi.inra@gmail.com, achbani105@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

On the base of prospecting conducted during the agriculture season 2012-2013, the results revealed that the olive knot disease caused by *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* was observed in different olive groves in Morocco. The disease incidence varies with location and cultivar. However, high disease incidence was reported in Taounate, Ouazzane and Meknes. The biochemical and the molecular tests were revealed the presence of saprophytic bacteria; *Pantoea agglomerans*, *Enterobacter* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., associated with *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi*. Moreover, a hypersensitive reaction on tobacco leaves caused by *Pantoea agglomerans* strains (2074-1 and 2074-4) was noted. Nonetheless, the strain of *Pantoea agglomerans* (2066-7) did not affect the tobacco leaves.

Keywords: Olive knots / *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *Savastanoi* / *Pantoea agglomerans* / molecular tests.

INTRODUCTION

Pseudomonas savastanoi are pathogens to plants of the *Oleaceae* family (Gardan *et al.* 1992). *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* (hereafter termed PSV) is specific to olive trees. The disease is widespread in olive producing Mediterranean countries and has recently been detected in Australia (Hall *et al.* 2004). Its symptoms are tumorous overgrowths occurring on young twigs, branches and

stems but occasionally on the leaves and fruits as well (Surico 1986). The knots develop in reaction to factors produced by the bacterium; including indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) and cytokinins (Comai and Kosuge 1980; Comai *et al.* 1982; Iacobellis *et al.* 1994; Surico and Iacobellis 1992). The length of the pathogen's incubation period and the size of the knot are regulated by the amounts of IAA and cytokinin, respectively. For many years, the phytohormones produced by PSV were considered to be its main virulence factors (Surico and Iacobellis 1992). More recently, however, products of the type III secretion system (TTSS), encoded by the *hrp/hrc* gene clusters and a variety of genes encoding *P. syringae* virulence determinants, have been discovered to play key roles in PSV pathogenicity (Rodríguez-Moreno *et al.* 2008; Sisto *et al.* 2004). In addition, other auxin-producing bacteria, such as *Pantoea agglomerans*, seem to interact with PSV and contribute to its pathogenesis (Cimmino *et al.* 2006; Marchi *et al.* 2006; Ouzari *et al.* 2008). 16S rDNA

How to cite this article:

Bouaichi .A, R. Benkirane, A.AMEUR, S.SADIK, A. Benbouazza, and E. H Achbani (2015). Characterization of *Pantoea agglomerans* Strains Isolated from Olive Knot disease in Morocco. *Biolife*, 3(2), pp 528-534. doi:10.17812/blj2015.32.26

Published online: June, 2015

sequence analysis revealed the presence of many saprophytic bacteria associated with PSV, such as *Pantoea agglomerans*, *Enterobacter* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *P. fluorescens*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* and *Burkholderia cepacia*. However, in the leaves, PSV was often associated with *Bacillus subtilis* and *Acinetobacter* species (Krid *et al.* 2010).

Pantoea agglomerans which is often associated with olive and oleander knots (Azad and Cooksey 1995; Fernandes and Marcelo 2002). It is also used as a biocontrol agent (Nunes *et al.* 2002; Trotel- Aziz *et al.* 2007), but apparently has a positive role in knot formation by producing IAA which contributes to increasing the size of knots (Marchi *et al.* 2006).

In this study we report (i) disease cartography of olive knot in different regions prospects in Morocco (ii) the isolation and characterization of some bacteria associated with PSV in knots of olive trees

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Olive knot disease cartography

Field prospections were conducted in 2012-2013 in several Morocco regions to make cartography of the different locations attacked. Prospections results are detailed in table 1.

Sampling procedures and isolation from knots

Sampling was released in the spring and autumn during 2012-2013. The knots were placed in sterile plastic bags, transported to the laboratory and processed immediately. The knots were surface-disinfected with a paper moistened with ethanol (Marchi *et al.* 2005). Small fragments (1–2 mm) were cut aseptically with a sterile scalpel then placed in 200 µl of sterile distilled water. After 30 min, a loopful of the resulting suspension was streaked with a

sterile loop onto the surface of *Kings B* (KB) medium containing gL⁻¹, 10 g protease peptone, 1.5 g K₂HPO₄, 1.5 g MgSO₄.7H₂O, 15 g agar and 15 ml glycerol, and the pH was adjusted to 7.2-7.4 (King *et al.* 1954). Plates were incubated at 25 ± 2°C for 72 hours and subjected to long wave (367 nm) dark blue ultra violet light for the detection of fluorescent colonies. The single fluorescent colonies were restreaked onto new KB plates and incubated at the same conditions. Fluorescent colonies were grown on KB test tubes and kept in refrigerator for further identification (Schaad, *et al.* 2001).

Pathogenicity test

A pathogenicity test was carried out on a limited number of samples, representing one isolate per locality. Wounds measuring around 1 cm were made in the bark of 1-year-old olive stems (Picholine marocaine) with a scalpel dipped in a bacterial suspension (10⁸ CFUml⁻¹) of pure culture grown for 48 h on *King's B* medium. Each isolate was inoculated at five wound sites. Wounds were protected with parafilm for 3 days. The inoculated trees were kept in a greenhouse at 24 ± 2°C and inspected for knot formation after 2 months. Negative control trees were inoculated with sterile distilled water.

Biochemical studies of endophytic bacteria associated with PSV

The following biochemical tests were performed: levan, oxidase, pectinolytic activity, and presence of arginine dehydrolase and tobacco hypersensitivity (LOPAT) according to Lelliott *et al.* (1966).

Hypersensitivity on *Nicotiana tabacum* (Klement *et al.* 1964) was tested with bacteria from 24 h *Kings B* medium suspended in sterile distilled water to a concentration of about 10⁸ CFU /ml. Control plants were injected with sterile distilled water. Reactions were considered positive if necrosis of infiltrated areas appeared within 48 h after injection.

Table-1. Different locations prospected and their incidences of Olive knot in Morocco

Isolate reference	region	Location	cultivars	Disease incidence	
2088	Taounate	bouhoda	Picholine marocaine	10%	
2064		bouaidal	Picholine marocaine	100%	
2075		Mrouz	Picholine marocaine	1%	
2076		askar	Picholine marocaine	50%	
2089		zrizar	Picholine marocaine	1%	
2090		zrizar	Picholine marocaine	60%	
2066		Mkabra	Menara	100%	
2065		Mkabra	Picholine marocaine	100%	
2074		Meknes	Sidi ali	Picholine marocaine	10%
2073			dkhissa	Picholine marocaine	100%
2102	lamhaya		Picholine marocaine	100%	
2107	Ouezzane	taoujtate	Picholine marocaine	50%	
2108		Bni kla	Picholine marocaine	40%	
2112		Bni kla	Picholine marocaine	30%	
2113		ouezzane	Menara	1%	

Three isolates were presumptively identified to species level using the multitube API 20E system (Biomérieux) following manufacturer's recommendations.

DNA Extraction and amplification

To complete the biochemical results, a molecular identification by sequencing was performed. The extraction was made using GenElute Mammalian Genomic Kit (Anonyme 2010). Quantification of DNA was performed using spectrophotometry. Amplification was performed with primers Fd1 (CAGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG) and RP2 (AGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG) at a PCR kit (Invitrogen). The PCR was carried out in a total volume of 25 µl of the following reaction mixture: 2.5µl 10X Buffer, 2µl dNTP (10mm), 0.125µl of each primer (100 µM), 0.75 µl MgCl₂ (50 mM), 0.2µl Taq (5U/µl) and 5µl DNA. The PCR was performed using the following protocol: initial denaturation at 96°C for 4 min, followed by 35 cycles of denaturation at 96°C for 0.1min, annealing at 52°C for 0.4min, and an extension at 72°C for 2min, followed by an additional extension at 72°C for 4 min. The PCR products (almost 1500 bp) were separated by gel electrophoresis on 1.5% agarose gel. Purification of PCR products was carried using the enzyme EXO-SAT according to the following schedule: 37°C for 15min following by 80°C for 15min.

Sequencing and Phylogenetic Analysis

Selected PCR fragments, amplified from the isolates tested for pathogenicity, were sequenced in both strands, with the pA and pH' primers, using the BigDye terminator cycle sequencing ready reaction FS kit. So the sequencing of amplification product was carried out in a total volume of 10µl of the

following reaction mixture: 1µl Big Dye, 3µl sequencing buffer x5, xµl primer (3.2-5pmol), (0.75-1.5) µl DNA matrice, (2.5-3.25) µl H₂O (MiliQ). The sequencing was performed using the following protocol: initial denaturation at 96°C for 1 min, followed by 25 cycles of denaturation at 96°C for 10s, annealing at 50°C for 5s, and an extension at 60°C for 4min, followed by an additional extension at 72°C for 4 min. Reading of sequencing results was done using NCBI-BLAST software (Altschul *et al.* 1997).

RESULTS

Olive Knots cartography

The conducted prospections in field of different regions in Morocco have shown that the disease is mainly located in the north of the country (Taounate, Ouezzane), it present again in the center (Meknes) (Figure-1). The progression of the disease in areas of central and northern of the country is favorites by climatic conditions (humidity and temperature).

Pathogenicity test

Sixty days after inoculation of 15 isolates on 1-year-old olive stems, five isolates (2064-8, 2065-1, 2065-2,2066-1,2066-2) caused the of olive knot symptoms (Figure.2)

Biochemical identification of endophytic bacteria associated with PSV

Bacterial colonies which were consistently isolated from the olive knots (2074-1, 2074-4) caused hypersensitive reaction (HR) on tobacco leaves (Figure-3) indicating that they are phytopathogenic bacteria.

Figure-1. Disease cartography of olive Knots of Moroccan prospected regions in 2012-2013

Figure-2. Symptoms on 1-year-old olive stems (Picholine marocaine) 60 days after inoculation with isolates 2064-8(a) and 2065-1, 2065-2 (b)

According to the OPAT tests, the 2074-1 and 2074-4 isolates were able to product Levan and positives for Oxidase, Pectinase and Arginine dihydrolase tests, but not for Tobacco test. However, the 2066-7 isolate were the same characteristic with a difference response concerned the Tobacco and Arginine dihydrolase tests.

Figure-3. Hypersensitivity reaction in tobacco caused by the isolates (2074-1, 2074-4)

Based on the results of biochemical analysis (gallery API20) ,Tow strains (2074-1,2074-4) showed ability to utilize Citrate (CIT), Sodium Piruvate (VP), Glucose (GLU), Man-nitol (MAN), Rhamnose (RHA), Sucrose (SAC), Melibiose (MEL), Ortho-Nitro-Phényl Galactoside (ONPG), Arabinose (ARA), and formation of indolepyruvic acid from tryptophan by desaminase tryptophan (TDA) however they aren't able to form the indole from tryptophan but they did not use Lysine (LDC), Ortni-thine (ODC), Gelatin (GEL), Inositol (INO), Thiosulfate (H2S) , Urea (URE), Sorbitol (SOR). However, the 2066-7 isolate were the same characteristic with a difference

response concerned the Ortho-Nitro-Phényl Galactoside (ONPG),Tryptophane désaminase (TDA), Glucose (GLU), Mannitol (MAN), Rhamnose (RHA), Sucrose (SAC), Melibiose (MEL), Arabinose (ARA) and Sodium Piruvate (VP) (Table 2).

Table-2. Biochemical characteristics of isolates (2074-1, 2074-4, and 2066-7) on gallery API20

Tests	desired character	2074-1	2074-4	2066-7
Levan	Levan production	(-)	(-)	(-)
Oxidase	Cytochrome-oxydase	(-)	(-)	(-)
Pectinase	Pectinase	(-)	(-)	(-)
ADH	Arginine dihydrolase	(-)	(-)	(+)
H. Tabac	hypersensitivity reaction in tobacco	(+)	(+)	(-)
ONPG	Beta-galactosidase	(+)	(+)	(-)
LDC	Lysine décarboxylase	(-)	(-)	(-)
ODC	Ornithine décarboxylase	(-)	(-)	(-)
CIT	Citrate utilization	(+)	(+)	(+)
H2S	H2S production	(-)	(-)	(-)
URE	Uréase	(-)	(-)	(-)
TDA	Tryptophane désaminase	(+)	(+)	(-)
IND	Indole production	(-)	(-)	(-)
VP	Sodium Piruvate	(+)	(+)	(-)
GEL	Gélatinase	(-)	(-)	(-)
GLU	Glucose	(+)	(+)	(-)
MAN	Mannitol	(+)	(+)	(-)
INO	inositol	(-)	(-)	(-)
SOR	Sorbitol	(-)	(-)	(-)

RHA	Rhamnose	(+)	(+)	(-)
SAC	Sucrose	(+)	(+)	(-)
MEL	Melibiose	(+)	(+)	(-)
AMY	Amygdaline	(-)	(-)	(-)
ARA	Arabinose	(+)	(+)	(-)
NO2	NO2 production	(-)	(-)	(-)
N2	N2 reduction	(-)	(-)	(-)

(-): Negative; (+): Positive.

Molecular identification

Result of DNA quantification showed that the quantity of DNA was sufficient for PCR. A band with 1500 bp size was observed in agarose gel (Figure. 4). Sequences of strains 2066-3, 2066-4 and (2066-7, 2074-1, 2074-4) were submitted to GenBank and were assigned respectively for accession numbers KF843716.1, KF782800.1 and HG799974.1.

Figure-4. Electrophoretic profile of (1), (2), (3) *Pantoea agglomerans* stains (4) *Pseudomonas sp.* (5) *enterobacter sp.* (6) Negative control (H₂O).

Based on the results of biochemical and sequence analysis of the 16S rDNA gene of strains 2066-3, 2066-4 and (2066-7, 2074-1, 2074-4), these isolates isolated was identified as *Enterobacter sp.*, *Pseudomonas sp* and *P. agglomerans* respectively (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

The present study demonstrated that the disease is widespread in Taounate, Ouezzane and Meknes regions. Thereby, we showed that “Picholine Marocain” is the most attacked variety by Knot disease than other varieties in Taounate and Meknes regions (table.1). In 1994 Benjama showed that this

variety was moderately sensitive of the disease, so our results can be explained by a genetically heterogeneous population of the variety and/or increased aggressiveness of the pathogen because of genetic changes.

60 bacteria were isolated from stem knots (Table. 1).Among the 36 fluorescent bacteria, were oxidase-negative, levan-negative, pectinolytic activity-negative, arginine dehydrolase-negative and tobacco hypersensitivity-positive (data not shown). Only 2066-7, 2074-1 and 2074-4 were not fluorescent. According to the analysis of the 16S rDNA sequence and biochemical tests (API20 gallery), 5 were identified as bacteria associated with the Pathogen. These associated bacteria are more abundant in knots than in leaves (Marchi *et al.* 2006).

HR reaction induced on tobacco leaves by *P. agglomerans* (2074-1, 2074-4) was put into evidence by other research (Moore 1979; Prinsen *et al.*1993).they showed that HR reaction on tobacco leaves is due to indolepyruvic acid formation from tryptophan by desaminase tryptophan. The indole-3-pyruvate (IPA) pathway is a major auxin pathway in plants. The IPA pathway could be shown in many bacteria such as phytopathogens (*P. agglomerans*), it consists of three steps. In a first step the precursor tryptophan is transaminated to IPA by an aminotransferase. In the rate-limiting step IPA is decarboxylated to indole-3-acetaldehyde (IAAld), which is then oxidized to IAA by a dehydrogenase. The decarboxylation step is catalyzed by the key enzyme indole-3-pyruvate decarboxylase. Inactivation of these genes results in impaired IAA production (sometimes >90%), indicating the importance of the encoded enzymes and consequently the IPA pathway in the IAA biosynthesis (Moore 1979; Prinsen *et al.* 1993).

In addition, the HR induced by the strains (2074-1, 2074-4) can be explained by the presence of a complete *hrp/hrc* gene clustern (Moretti *et al.* 2014). *hrp* gene clusters encode components of a type III protein secretion system that is believed to be used by phytopathogenic bacteria to transport, directly into the host cells, virulence proteins which are ultimately responsible for leakage of plant nutrients to the extracellular space of infected tissues and suppression of host defenses (Sisto *et al.* 2004 ; Greenberg and Vinatzer 2003).

Table-3. Endophytic bacteria associated with PSV revealed 16S rDNA sequence analysis

Isolate reference	Closest species using 16S rDNA sequences	GenBank Accession Numbers	Similarity (%)
2066-3	<i>Enterobacter sp.</i>	KF843716.1	99
2066-4	<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	KF782800.1	100
2074-1,2074-4,2066-7	<i>Pantoea agglomerans</i>	HG799974.1	100

Competition of *P. agglomerans* with PSV was probably for nutrients and space and perhaps more intensively, by means of the production of antibiotic substances (Marchi *et al.* 2006). The positive role of *P. agglomerans* in knot formation in certain cases was mostly probably caused by an increased accumulation of IAA at the sites where it multiplied together with PSV. In culture, *P. agglomerans* accumulated not only indole-3-aldehyde, an alternate end-product of the oxidation of IAA (Moore, 1979), and indole-3-ethanol, a shunt product of the biosynthesis of IAA from tryptophan via indolpyruvic acid (Moore, 1979), but also IAA in amounts similar to those reported for some virulent PSV strains (Surico *et al.* 1985). *Pantoea agglomerans* has often been reported to be associated with olive and oleander knots (Azad and Cooksey 1995; Fernandes and Marcelo 2002; Surico and Lavermicocca 1989). The bacterium is considered an epiphyte and is very common on the aerial parts of plants (Starr and Chatterjee, 1972). Three pathovars of *P. agglomerans* have been described, pv. *Gypsophilae* (Brown 1932), pv. *Betae* (Burr *et al.* 1991) and pv. *Milletiae* (Opgenorth *et al.* 1994); all these pathovars cause diseases characterized by galls similar to the knots caused by PSV.

Moreover, the strain 2066-7 of *P. agglomerans* showed an antagonist effect against phytopathogenic bacteria. Thus *P. agglomerans* 2066-7 was revealed its potential biocontrol against many phytopathogenic bacteria *in vitro* and *in planta*. Its utilization allowed a reduction of Soft Rot Disease in Potato Caused by *Pectobacterium carotovorum* (Faquih *et al.* 2014) and Bacterial Onion Diseases Caused by *Pseudomonas marginalis*, *Pseudomonas viridiflava*, *Xanthomonas retroflexus* and *Pantoea ananatis* (Sadik *et al.* 2015).

The strain 2066-7 also revealed its contribution to improving the growth and yield of some crops such as Potato culture (Faquih *et al.* 2014 and Dalal boudoudou *et al.* 2015). This strain 2066-7 was revealed an antagonist effect against other phytopathogenic bacteria (data not shown).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our study showed that tumors of the knot disease are rich in olive endophytic bacteria associated with PSV. Then, future studies would focus on the study the Effects of co-inoculation of PSV and the *P. agglomerans* on the growth dynamics of these bacteria Strains of PSV and of the *P. agglomerans* were inoculated either alone or in combination in the stems of 1-year-old self-rooted olive cuttings "Picholine Marocain" in early spring. Also, the 2066-7 strain can be used like a base of a biopesticide product.

Acknowledgments

We gratefully acknowledge the reception of the Laboratory of Phytobacteriology and Biocontrol, National Institute of Agronomic Research, Meknes and Laboratory of Botany, Biotechnology and Plant Protection, Kenitra, Morocco.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

References

1. Altschul, S.F., Madden, T.L., Schaffer, A.A., Zhang, J., Zhang, Z., Miller, W. and Lipman, D.J. 1997. Gapped BLAST and PSI-BLAST: a new generation of protein database search programs. *Nucleic Acids Res* 25, 3389–3402.
2. Anonyme, 2010. *GenElute™ Mammalian Genomic DNA Miniprep Kit, User Guide*, 16p.
3. Azad, H.R. and Cooksey, D.A., 1995. A semiselective medium for detecting epiphytic and systemic populations of *Pseudomonas savastanoi* from oleander. *Phytopathology* 85, 740-745.
4. Benjama, A. 1994. Étude de la sensibilité variétale de l'olivier au Maroc vis-à-vis de *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *savastanoi* agent de la tuberculose. *Cahiers Agricultures*, 3, pp. 405-408.
5. Brown, N.A. 1932. A gall similar to crown gall produced on *Gypsophila* by a new bacterium. *Journal of Agricultural Research* 48, 1099–112.
6. Burr, T.J, Katz, B.H., Abawi, G.S. and Crosier, D 1991. Comparison of tumorigenic strains of *Erwinia herbicola* isolated from table beet to *E. herbicola* pv. *gypsophilae*. *Plant Disease* 75, 855-8.
7. Cimmino, A., Andolfi, A., Marchi, G. and Surico, G. 2006. Phytohormone production by strains of *Pantoea agglomerans* from knots on olive plants caused by *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi*. *Phytopathol Mediterr* 45, 247–252.
8. Comai, L. and Kosuge, T. 1980. Involvement of plasmid deoxyribonucleic acid in indoleacetic acid synthesis in *Pseudomonas savastanoi*. *J Bacteriol* 143, 950-957.
9. Comai, L., Surico, G. and Kosuge, T. 1982. Relation of plasmid DNA to indoleacetic acid production in different strains of *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *savastanoi*. *J Gen Microbiol* 128, 2157–2163
10. Dalal BOUDOUDOU, Anas FADLI, Abdelhak TALHA, Younes BOURACHDI, Allal DOUIRA and Hamid BENYAHIA (2015). Effect of seasonal and citrus rootstocks on inoculum density of *Phytophthora* spp. in citrus orchard in a heavy soil of the Gharb region of Morocco. *Biolife*, 3(2), pp 367-377. doi:10.17812/blj2015.32.4a
11. Faquih, H., Ait Mhand, R. Ennaji, M. Benbouaza, A and Achbani, E. 2014. *Aureobasidium pullulans* (De Bary) G. Arnaud, a Biological Control against Soft Rot Disease in Potato Caused by *Pectobacterium carotovorum*, *International Journal of Science and Research*. 3(10) pp. 1779-1786.
12. Fernandes, A. and Marcelo, M. 2002. A possible synergistic effect of *Erwinia* sp on the development of

- olive knot symptoms caused by *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *savastanoi* in *Olea europea*. *Acta Horticulturae* 586, 729-731.
13. Gardan, L., Bollet, C., Abu-Ghorrah, M., Grimont, F. and Grimont, P. 1992. DNA relatedness among the pathovar strains of *Pseudomonas syringae* subsp. *savastanoi* Janse (1982) and proposal of *Pseudomonas savastanoi* sp. nov. *Int J Syst Bacteriol* 42,606-612.
 14. Greenberg, J. T. and Vinatzer, B. A. 2003. Identifying type III effectors of plant pathogens and analyzing their interaction with plant cells. *Curr. Opin. Microbiol.* 6,20-28.
 15. Hall, B.H., Coter, E.J., Whattman, M., Noble, D., Luck, J. and Cartwright, D. 2004. First report of olive knot disease on olives (*Olea europea*) in Australia. *Austral Plant Pathol* 33, 433–436.
 16. Iacobellis, N.S., Sisto, A., Surico, G., Evidente, A. and DiMaio, E. 1994. Pathogenicity of *Pseudomonas syringae* subsp. *savastanoi* mutants defective in phytohormone production. *J Phytopathol* 140,238–248.
 17. King, E.O., Ward, M.K and Raney, D.E. 1954. Two simple media for the demonstration of pyocyanin and fluorescein. *Journal of Laboratory and Clinical Medicine* 44, 301-307.
 18. Klement, Z., Farkas, G. L. and Lovrekovich, L. 1964. Hypersensitive reaction induced by phytopathogenic bacteria in the tobacco leaf. *Phytopathology* 54, 474-477.
 19. Krid, S., Rhouma, A., Mogou, I., Quesada, J.M., Nesme, X. and Gargouri, A. 2010. *Pseudomonas savastanoi* endophytic bacteria in olive tree knot and antagonistic potential of strains of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and *Bacillus subtilis*, *Journal of Plant Pathology* 92 (2), 335-341.
 20. Lelliott, R.A., Billing E. and Hayward, A.C. 1966. A determinative scheme for the fluorescent plant pathogenic *pseudomonads*. *Journal of Applied Bacteriology* 29, 470-489.
 21. Marchi, G., Sisto, A., Cimmino, A., Andolfi, A., Cipriani, M.G., Evidente, A., Surico G., 2006. Interaction between *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* and *Pantoea agglomerans* in olive knots. *Plant Pathology* 55, 614-624.
 22. Marchi, G., Viti, C., Giovannetti, L. and Surico G. 2005. Spread of levan-positive populations of *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* the causal agent of olive knot, in central Italy *European Journal of Plant Pathology* 112, 101-112.
 23. Mendes, R., Pizzirani-Kleiner, A.A., Araujo, W.L. and Raaijmakers J.M. 2007. Diversity of cultivated endophytic bacteria from sugarcane: genetic and biochemical characterization of *Burkholderia cepacia* complex isolates. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 73, 7259-7267.
 24. Moore, T.C. 1979. *Biochemistry and Physiology of Plant Hormones*. New York-Heidelberg-Berlin: Springer Verlag. NY. Pp: 37.
 25. Moretti, C., Cortese, C., Passos da Silva, D., Venturi, V., Torelli, E., Firrao, G and Buonauro, R. 2014. Draft genome sequence of a hypersensitive reaction-inducing *Pantoea agglomerans* strain isolated from olive knots caused by *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi*. *Genome Announc.* 2(4), e00774-14.
 26. Nunes, C., Usall, J., Teixidó, N., Fons, E. and Viñas, I. 2002. Postharvest biological control by *Pantoea agglomerans* (CPA-2) on Golden Delicious apples. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 92, 247-255.
 27. Opgenorth, D.C., Henderson, T.M. and Clark, E. 1994. First report of a bacterial gall of a *Wisteria sinensis* caused by *Erwinia herbicola* pv. *milletiae* in California. *Plant Disease* 78, 12-17.
 28. Ouzari, H., Khsairi, A., Raddadi, N., Jaoua, L., Hassen, A., Zarrouk, M., Daffonchio, D. and Boudabous, A. 2008. Diversity of auxin producing bacteria associated to *Pseudomonas savastanoi*-induced olive knots. *J Basic Microbiol*, 48, 1–8.
 29. Prinsen, E., Costacurta, A., Michiels, K., Vanderleyden, J. and Van Onckelen, H. 1993. Azospirillum brasilense indole-3-acetic acid biosynthesis: evidence for a non-tryptophan dependent pathway. *Mol Plant-Microbe Interact* 6, 609–615.
 30. Rodríguez-Moreno, L., Barceló-Munõz, A. and Ramos, C. 2008. In vitro analysis of the interaction of *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* and *nerii* with micropropagated olive plants. *Phytopathology*, 98, 815–822.
 31. Sadik, S., Mazouz, H., Bouaichi, A., Benbouazza, A. and Achbani, E.H. 2015. Biological control of bacteria onion diseases using a bacterium, *Pantoea agglomerans* 2066-7 S. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 4(1), pp.103-111.
 32. Schaad, N.W., Jones, J. B. and Chun, W. 2001. *Laboratory Guide for Identification of Plant Pathogenic bacteria*. 2nd ed. *Aps. Press*. pp 373.
 33. Sisto, A., Cipriani, M.G. and Morea, M. 2004. Knot formation caused by *Pseudomonas syringae* subsp. *savastanoi* on olive plants is *hrp*-dependent. *Phytopathology*, 94, 484-489.
 34. Spaepen, S. and Vanderleyden, J. 2010. Auxin and Plant-Microbe Interactions. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Biol* 2011; doi: 10.1101/cshperspect.a001438.
 35. Starr, M.P. and Chatterjee, A.K. 1972. The genus *Erwinia*: enterobacteria pathogenic to plants and animals. *Annual Review of Microbiology* 26, 389–426.
 36. Surico, G. 1986. Indoleacetic acid and cytokinins in the olive knot disease. An overview of their role and their genetic determinants. In *Biology and Molecular Biology of Plant– Pathogen Interactions*, Vol. H1 ed. Bailey, J. pp. 315–329 NATO ASI Series. Germany: Springer-Verlag, Berlin.
 37. Surico, G. and Iacobellis, N.S. 1992. Phytohormones and olive knot disease. In: Verma DPS (ed) *Molecular signals in plant–microbe communications*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, pp 209–229.

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7270238>

Received: 6 April 2015;

Accepted: 13 May 2015;

Available online : 7 June 2015